

QUIZ**LAST NAME: Amara****FIRST NAME: Patrick****PROGRAM CODE: MDIA****COURSE CODE : ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. Which of the answers mentioned below bears an irrelevant information to research paper?

- Anecdotal information and superlative.¹
- Consistent and accurate information.
- Clear information of your reference material.
- Comprehensive and detailed oriented information.

2. What is the relevance of style guide in contemporary academic and professional writing?

- Style helps to establish the writer's place in the world.²
- Style is important because it is a natural trend of writing.

¹ Cleenewerck Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1* (Bangui: Central Africa Republic: Euclid University, 2020), 6.

² Sebranek Patrick, Dave Kemper, and Verne Mayer, *Write Source 2000* (Massachusetts: Great Source Education Group, 1999), 69.

- Style is of no relevance in academic and professional writing.
 - Style makes a writer over presents his or her information.
3. **In academic and professional writing concept, which of the undermentioned definitions correctly defines plagiarism?**
- When a writer accurately credits the author whose information he or she is using.
 - When a writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author whose information he or she used.³**
 - Whet a writer systemically and accurately present his or her source.
 - When a writer over emphasizes the importance of his or her works.
4. **Which of the following is not a sanction for plagiarism?**
- Failing grades and possible expulsion.
 - Lower your grades in assignment and quizzes.
 - Loss of credibility and professional standing.
 - Plagiarism establishes your professional in academia.⁴**
5. **What are the components of good argument?**
- Opinion, qualifier, support, concession.⁵**
 - Research, opinion, information, conclusion.

³ Cleenewerck Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 5.

⁴ Cleenewerck Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 4* (Bangui: Central Africa Republic: Euclid University, 2020), 6.

⁵ Sebranek Patrick, Dave Kemper, and Verne Mayer, 122.

- Qualifier, quotation, research, conclusion.
 - Explanation, support, citation, research.
6. **With special reference to Kate L. Turabian, “Manual for Writers” 8th Edition, which of the undermentioned is not true about citation in literary works?**
- Correct citations help you to avoid plagiarism and its related consequences.
 - Citations give disrepute to the author whose information you use for your project.⁶**
 - It gives the readers of your work the opportunity to locate your source.
 - It gives readers the opportunity to crosscheck your facts.
7. **As a standard for academic writing, all sources must be cited, but when is it not necessary to cite a source?**
- When the source of your information is can only be found on the internet.
 - When the source of your information is giving to you by your Instructor.
 - When the information is based on common knowledge and it is available in many sources related to your topic.⁷**
 - When writing on a topic that is based on your coursepack.

⁶ Kate L. Turabain, *A Manual for Writers Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. Revised by Weyne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, Williams T. Fitzgerald, and the University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2013), 234.

⁷ Cleenewerck Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period I*, 5-6.

8. **The ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 5, covers two critical components of the European Commission, what are they?**
- Resolution of European wars and sustainable peace.
 - Detail Linguistic convention and the history, formation, and workings of the union.⁸**
 - Ethnic and cultural diversity in Europe.
 - Components and structures of the Commission.
9. **What are the structures of a good essay?**
- Introduction, citation, and conclusion.
 - Reading, citation, and presentation.
 - Presentation, introduction, and conclusion.
 - Introduction, body, and conclusion.⁹**
10. **What variant of English Language does the English style guide, based on?**
- British English Language.¹⁰**
 - American English Language.
 - European English Language.
 - Canadian English Language.

⁸ Cooper Tim et al., *English Style Guide. A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission. Seventh Edition.* (European Commission, Director General for Translation, 2011), 1.

⁹ Sebranek Patrick, Dave Kemper, and Verne Mayer, 112.

¹⁰ Cooper Tim et al., 1.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.